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Working paper

INVENTORY OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY AND HEALTH SURVEYS

Milestone 21.9 of WP 21

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Abstract

This working paper is part of Work Package 21 'Innovative tools and protocols for working conditions and vulnerability research' of the InGRID project. It aims to discuss an inventory of working conditions and occupational safety and health surveys in Europe. Together with the inventories on linked employer-employee surveys and on policy data bases on working conditions and OSH that are made within the project, this inventory wants to provide researchers across Europe with an overview of existing surveys, and the quality of these surveys as a starting point for further integration and optimisation of the existing tools for working conditions research.

The inventory bundles 17 national and transnational surveys on working conditions and OSH in European countries, which focus on individuals (employees), covering 11 European countries. It provides an overview of some relevant survey characteristics and survey quality information, such as survey methodology (timing, frequency, population, design), data collection and survey questionnaire, survey sample and response, scope of the survey (objectives and topics covered), available survey documentation, data availability, and quality control procedures. Finally some general conclusions are made based on the overview and some limitations of the inventory are discussed.

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This report constitutes Milestone 21.9 'Inventory of WC & OSH surveys', for Work Package 21 'Innovative tools and protocols for working conditions and vulnerability research' of the InGRID project.

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of life or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimize these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

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List of abbreviations

AID	Arbeids - og inkluderingsdepartementet
AK	Arbeitskammer
AV	Swedish Work Environment Authority
BAD	Balkan Institute for labour and social policy
BAuA	Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health
BIBB	Federal Institute for Vocational Training Affairs
CAPI	Computer Assisted Personal Interview
CATI	Computer Assisted Telephone Interview
CAWI	Computer Assisted Web Interview
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Sciences Data Archives
CSB	Central Statistical Office
Dares	Directorate for Research, Studies and Statistics
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DGAFP	General Directorate of Administration and the Public Sector
DGT	General Directorate of labour
ESF	European Social Fund
ESS	European Social Survey
EU	European Union
Eurofound	European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions
EWCS	European Working Conditions Survey
FAS	Swedish Council for Working Life and Social Research
FIOH	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health
GESIS	Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
GmbH	Gesundheitsvorsorge und sicherheitstechnik
IAB	Institute for Employment Research
IFES	Institute for Empirical Social Research
ILO	International Labour Organisation
InGRID	Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion
INSHT	Instituto Nacional de Seguridad e Higiene en el Trabajo
ISFOL	The institute for the Development of vocational Training of Workers
JWES model	Job content, Working conditions, Employment conditions and Social relations model
LFS	Labour Force Survey
MEE	Ministry of Employment and Economy
NRCWE	National Research Centre for the Working Environment
NSD	Norwegian Social Science Data Services
OSH	Occupational Safety and Health
PAPI	Paper Assisted Personal Interview
PATI	Paper Assisted Telephone Interview
SAQ	Self-Administered Questionnaire
SCB	Statistics Sweden
SRS	Simple Random Sampling
SSB	Statistics Norway
STAMI	Statens instituttet for arbeidsmiljøforskning
SZW	Ministry of social affairs and employment
VR	Swedish Research Council

WES model
XML

Work organisation, Employment conditions and Social relations model
eXtensible Mark-up Language

1. Introduction

1.1 Context of research

This working paper was written for the InGRID project¹ (Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion). The project can be situated within the context of the inclusive growth priority of the Europe 2020 strategy, the growth strategy of the European Union. In this strategy, the EU has set five ambitious objectives - on employment, innovation, education, social inclusion and climate/energy - to be reached by 2020. The 'EU Employment Package contributing to more and better jobs' was developed to complement the EU2020 strategy and the agenda for new skills and new jobs. With this Employment Package, the European Commission wants to boost job creation and to focus on job-rich growth (COM 2020 final, 2010; European Commission, 2013) as well as to ensure the quality of new jobs. To evaluate this strategy and the progress, good measurement tools and indicators are necessary.

This is where the InGRID project aims to contribute. The general objective is to integrate and innovate existing but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on 'poverty and living conditions' and on 'working conditions and vulnerability. In this regards, specific attention is among others given to better measurement and indicators. In this light one of the task within Work Package 21 'Innovative tools and protocols for working conditions and vulnerability research' is to integrate existing repositories on working conditions and occupational safety and health (OSH). This working paper discusses the first of three inventories related to working conditions and OSH in Europe. The inventory bundles national and transnational surveys on working conditions and OSH in European countries, which focus on individuals (employees). In next working papers, an inventory of linked employer-employee surveys and an inventory of policy data bases on working conditions and OSH will be discussed.

1.2 Working conditions and occupational safety and health in short

Working conditions is a frequently used concept which covers a broad range of aspects related to work. Nevertheless, it is difficult to find a clear and straightforward definition of this concept. Van Houten, Cabrita and Vargas (Eurofound, 2014b) look at working conditions as "*the result of interaction between characteristics of a job, the work, the company and the individual.*" This includes work-related aspects such as working time and working hours, income, work-life balance, work organisation (team work, autonomy, multitasking, etc.), skills and training, employee representation, psychological and physical environment, etc. In the European industrial relations glossaries,² Eurofound gives the following definition of working conditions: "*Conditions in and under which work is performed as regards the work environment and the time, place and organization of work. [...] Nowadays, [...] a broader definition of the term is coming to be accepted which also includes the economic dimension and its effects on living conditions and the social roles of employees.*"

Working conditions are often mentioned in one go with the concept of job quality or quality of work. Green defines job quality as "*the extent to which a job has work and employment-related factors that foster beneficial outcomes for the employee, particularly psychological well-being, physical well-being and positive attitudes such as job satisfaction.*" (Green, 2006, in Holman 2012). Working conditions thus can be seen as several

1 www.inclusivegrowth.be

2 <http://eurofound.europa.eu/efemiredictionary/working-conditions>

factors determining the quality of work. Job quality and working conditions are also brought in relation with outcomes, like health aspects, (job)satisfaction and work attitudes (Holman, 2012).

The list of working conditions is long and there is a large variety amongst them. Within the job quality research tradition several attempts have been done to group all the different working conditions and work-related factors into dimensions or groups. One of these attempts is the classification of Green and Mostafa (Eurofound, 2012b) who list three areas of job quality: work quality, employment quality and empowerment quality. Another model is the JWES model which outlines four dimensions (job content, working conditions, employment conditions and social relations) covering all types of working (Vandenbrande et al., 2012) or the more limited and related WES model with three dimension: work organisation (covering job content and working conditions), employment conditions and social relations (Ramioul, Szekér, & Vandekerckhove, Forthcoming). Table 1.1 shows a list of working conditions that can be allocated to these three dimensions. However this list is not exhaustive.

Table 1.1 Working conditions and work-related aspects and the three dimensions of the WES model

Work organisation	Employment conditions	Social relations
Task autonomy	Wage	Voice
Task complexity	Permanent contract	Say
Autonomous team work	Full time work	Social support
Planning autonomy	Variable working time arrangements	Supportive management
Repetitive tasks	Atypical working time arrangements	Violence and harassment
Emotional pressure	Career opportunities	
Dealing with people	Training	
Speed pressure		
Risks (ergonomic, ambient and bio-chemical)		
Fixed workplace		

Source Ramioul, Szekér, & Vandekerckhove, 2014

These models of job quality allow us to look at working conditions from a broad perspective by taking the employment conditions and social relations into account. This broad perspective will allow us to evaluate the scope of each of the surveys and get a clear picture on which aspects they try to cover in the survey. Therefore we will also look at the outcomes related to working conditions and job quality that are assessed in the surveys.

The ILO (Alli, 2008) defines occupational safety and health(OSH) as follows: *“the science of the anticipation, recognition, evaluation and control of hazards arising in or from the workplace that could impair the health and well-being of workers, taking into account the possible impact on surrounding communities and the general environment.”*

OSH thus is strongly related with working conditions such as risks, emotional pressure, speed pressure, etc. However, the domain of OSH is much broader and also includes measures taken to promote health and safety. It also requires an assessment of for example the health status (and changes in it), accidents, work-related health problems, absenteeism, etc. Therefore we will also evaluate to which extent the surveys question OSH issues.

1.3 Scope of the working paper

In this working paper an overview will be given of currently active national surveys on working conditions and OSH. Further their methodology, data, topics and objectives, sample size, etc. will be compared. Next to this, metadata on the latest version of each of the surveys is produced and available in Nesstar format.

In the next chapter we will first go more into detail about the methodology used and give some clarification on the metadata and Nesstar tool. The third chapter is devoted to the comparison of the included national surveys on working conditions and OSH. This starts with a general description of the surveys and their organisers and funding. Secondly, the survey methodology is discussed focusing on the timing and frequency of the survey, the survey population and survey design. The third part looks at the data collection mode and the questionnaire. Afterwards the sampling method, sample size and response rates are commented. In the next part, the survey objectives are listed, as well as the topics covered in each of the surveys. Following this an overview is given of the available survey documentation. Finally the quality control procedures used are discussed.

Some preliminary remarks can be made regarding this inventory. First, in most cases only the information on the latest version of the survey is included. When substantial changes over time are made, these might also be discussed when relevant. However the focus of this working paper is to provide an overview of the current available national surveys. Therefore a focus on the latest version is relevant. Second, no references are included in the tables to enhance the readability of the tables. Otherwise the tables would be covered with references and the actual content and purpose (overview, comparability, etc.) might be lost. In appendix 1, the used references for each of the surveys are listed. A third remark is that the tables often only use the abbreviations of the surveys. In the first overview table of the surveys both the whole name and the abbreviation of the survey are given. Most of the used abbreviations are the official abbreviations. In some cases, when no abbreviation exists, an abbreviation was made for sake of simplicity.

2. Methodology and inventory

2.1 Selection of the surveys and search criteria

For this inventory, 17 surveys were selected based on a set of criteria. The first criterion is topical. Surveys with a focus on working conditions and on occupational safety and health (OSH) are selected. Secondly, only national or transnational surveys in European countries are included, which focus on the national level and cover (almost) all groups of employees and sectors. Only recent surveys, which have taken place in the last five years, are selected. Another criterion is that there is more than one wave done or planned in the near future.

The surveys were selected by consulting the three Eurofound studies (Eurofound, 2003, 2007f, 2014a) on working conditions surveys and other Eurofound reports which discuss findings from these national surveys. Other studies on working conditions were consulted to identify national surveys and collect documentation on these surveys. National and transnational data archives (such as CESSDA) were also used. Besides this, only the surveys for which some documentation in English, French, German or Dutch could be found were included.

2.2 Metadata and Nesstar inventory

2.2.1 Metadata

Metadata are data about data. It is a set of data that provides (descriptive) information on for example the application of data, content of data, data producers, etc. *“Metadata is structured information that describes, explains, locates, or otherwise makes it easier to retrieve, use or manage an information resource.”* (National Information Standards Organization (U.S.), 2004).

Creating descriptive metadata for an inventory starts with deciding which information will be listed and which template will be used. Since the InGRID project among others wants to harmonise the existing European data infrastructures and enhance comparability, it seems appropriate to look for international used standards for metadata and ensure the alignment of the created metadata with existing metadata in European archives (ICPSR, 2012).

Web search and consultation of major and prominent European data archives in social sciences, show a widespread use of the DDI (Data Documentation Initiative) standards as well as the Nesstar tool to produce and publish metadata, and make it available online. Therefore, it seems appropriate to follow this trend and develop the metadata of the InGRID inventories according to DDI standards, using the Nesstar publisher software.

2.2.2 Data Documentation Initiative (DDI)

Within the social sciences research field, the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) provides metadata specifications for creating metadata for datasets (www.ddialliance.org). Together with many other initiatives, the DDI aims to create an international standard for describing data from social, behavioural and economic sciences. The DDI is used by many social science data archives in the world, and provides an international XML-based (eXtensible Mark-up Language) descriptive metadata standard. The use of XML-code enables easy internet access of the data and metadata, and makes

them machine readable and processable. It allows creating a single document, including all information and key data documentation, creating a richer and more comprehensive content about data. The data and metadata can be viewed online, used for sub setting and online analysis or downloaded, ... The standard and codebooks allow for metadata and data to be exchanged, as well as precision in searching through the tagging system in the code. The DDI aims to support the entire research data life cycle.

Backside of the XML-code, is the complexity of the language, which makes it less easy and accessible to read and write. However, several tools are developed to facilitate this, such as codebooks, software, etc.

2.2.3 Nesstar

Nesstar is a software system for data publishing and online analysis (www.nesstar.com). It exists of three linked software tools: Nesstar Publisher, Nesstar Server and Nesstar Web View. Nesstar is owned by Norwegian Social Science Data Services (NSD)

(<http://www.nsd.uib.no/nsd/english/index.html>).

Nesstar Publisher is freeware and allows importing, preparing and publishing data, including metadata (using DDI standards). It is a complete metadata authoring tool. Files can also again be exported or pdf documents can be created, summarizing the content of the nesstar file. Using the Nesstar Server, these data and documentation files can be provided online, using a web server. With Nesstar Web view users can search for data, browse datasets, analyse and download data online.

Examples of data archives using nesstar are:

- CESSDA (<http://www.cessda.net/catalogue/>);
- UK Data Services (<http://nesstar.ukdataservice.ac.uk/webview/>);
- NSD (<http://nsddata.nsd.uib.no/webview/>);
- GESIS (<http://zocat.gesis.org/webview/>);
- ESS (<http://nesstar.ess.nsd.uib.no/webview/>);
- and many others.

For the creation of the inventory and metadata, Nesstar Publisher will be used. No knowledge of XML is needed, and DDI documented datasets can be easily imported, created and edited.

2.2.4 Nesstar Publisher

Nesstar Publisher can be downloaded and is freeware. Once installed on the computer, it is easy useable and accessible. Metadata files retrieved from other data archives can be imported easily and adjusted if necessary. It is easy to organise all documentations in folders. New datasets and documentations can be created easily. Table a1.1 in the appendix gives an overview of the topics and information that can be included.

2.2.5 Inventory of national surveys on working conditions and occupational safety and health issues

Next to this working paper, an inventory is created using Nesstar. This inventory includes the metadata of the last edition of each of the discussed surveys. Where already available, the metadata of earlier editions are already included. With time, this inventory might be expanded with the metadata of all the earlier editions of the surveys.

3. Comparison and overview of the surveys

3.1 The surveys

3.1.1 Selection of national surveys on working conditions and OSH

The scope of this inventory is on national or transnational working conditions surveys in European countries, which focus on the national level and cover (almost) all groups of employees and sectors. Further, the survey must have taken place within the last five years and more than one wave has to be done or planned in the near future. With this in mind 17 recent surveys were selected, covering 11 European countries.

In some countries more than one survey was selected (Austria, Finland, France, Italy and Spain). Further, some surveys changed names over time - sometimes linked with changes in the survey scope or methodology. However, because these surveys and the results are to some extent comparable over time, previous versions of the surveys are included in this overview. Since methodology, sample, questionnaires in some cases changed over different versions, they are discussed separately when necessary.

- the Working Environment and Health in Denmark (WEHD) study is a continuation of the Danish Employee study (WEC), later called the Danish Work Environment Cohort Study (DWECS). Differences between the WEC and DWECS are very limited and therefore they will be discussed together. The WEHD differs more from its predecessors and will be discussed separately;
- the Swedish Longitudinal Occupational Survey of Health (SLOSH) is a continuation of the Swedish Work Environment Surveys (SWES). Since the SLOSH is a distinct project from the SWES, it is also useful to discuss this survey separately;
- the Germany BIBB/IAB survey changed name due to a change in the funding and organisers of this survey, and is now called the Germany BIBB/BAuA survey. The changes are mainly directed towards the change in name and funding, and there was only a limited impact on the survey itself. Therefore they will not be discussed individually;
- the Netherlands Working Conditions Survey (NEA) has a subset which follows a cohort between 2007 and 2009, the NEA-cohort study. However, since this cohort is incorporated in the NEA itself, it is not necessary to discuss it separately.

Table 3.1 gives an overview of the selected surveys (and their predecessors), with their original name in the language of the country and an abbreviation.³ These abbreviations will be used throughout the report.

The table and figure 3.1 show the countries in which working conditions are regularly questioned using a national survey. Not surprisingly, the Scandinavian countries with a long tradition in research and surveys on working conditions (Finland, Denmark, Sweden and Norway) are all represented with one or several surveys. Also in continental Europe, these surveys are rather widespread (France, Austria, Germany, the Netherlands). In the Southern European countries, except Spain and Italy, and

³ Where available the (English version of the) official abbreviation of the survey name is used. When there was no abbreviation available or used in related documents, the survey name was abbreviated using the first letter of the words included in the English version of the survey name. These abbreviations are indicated in the table.

Eastern European countries, except Bulgaria, surveys on working conditions are much less prevalent. This can however partly be related to problems in identifying the surveys due to language issues. Only those surveys for which at least some information was available in English, French, German or Dutch are included in this report.

Figure 3.1 Countries for which a national survey is included

Table 3.1 Overview of the selected surveys

N°	Survey	Original name	Abbreviation	Country
1	Austrian Occupational health monitor	Österreichische Arbeitsgesundheitsmonitor	AOHM*	Austria (AT)
2	Austrian Work Climate Index	Österreichische Arbeitsklima Index	AI	Austria (AT)
3	National Working Conditions Survey in Bulgaria	НАЦИОНАЛНО ИЗСЛЕДВАНЕ НА УСЛОВИЯТА НА ТРУД В БЪЛГАРИЯ	NWCS BG*	Bulgaria (BG)
4	Working Environment and Health in Denmark	Arbejds miljø	WEHD	Denmark (DK)
4b	<i>Previously: Danish Employee Study and later the Danish Work Environment Cohort Study⁴</i>	<i>Den Nationale Arbejds miljøkohorte (NÅK)</i>	<i>WEC/DWECS</i>	<i>Denmark (DK)</i>
5	Finnish National Work and health survey	Työ ja Terveys – Haastattelututkimus	FNWHS*	Finland (FI)
6	Finnish Quality of work life surveys ^o		FQWLS	Finland (FI)
7	Finnish Working Life Barometer		WLB	Finland (FI)
8	The Medical Monitoring Survey of Professional Risks	Surveillance Médicale des Expositions aux Risques Professionnels	SUMER	France (FR)
9	L'enquête Conditions de travail	L'enquête Conditions de Travail	CT	France (FR)
10	Germany BIBB/BAuA Survey <i>Previously BIBB/LAB Survey</i>	Erwerbstätigenbefragung - Arbeit und Beruf im Wandel, Erwerb und Verwertung beruflicher Qualifikationen	BIBB/BAuA survey	Germany (DE)
11	PLUS - Participation, labour, unemployment survey		ISFOL PLUS*	Italy (IT)
12	Quality of work survey	La qualità del lavoro	ISFOL QWS*	Italy (IT)
13	Netherlands working conditions survey, <i>including the NEA-cohort study</i>	Nationale Enquête Arbeidsomstandigheden (- cohort)	NEA	The Netherlands (NL)
14	Level of Living Survey, Working Conditions		LKU	Norway (NO)
15	National Survey on Working Conditions	Encuesta Nacional de Condiciones de Trabajo	ENCT	Spain (ES)
16	Quality of working life survey	Encuesta de Calidad de Vida en Eltrabajo	ECVT	Spain (ES)
17	Swedish Longitudinal occupational survey of Health	Riksrepresentativ longitudinell arbetsmiljöundersökning	SLOSH	Sweden (SE)
17b	<i>Previously: Swedish work environment surveys⁵</i>	<i>Arbetsmiljöundersökningen (AMU)</i>	<i>SWES</i>	<i>Sweden (SE)</i>

* = non official abbreviation

^o Used to be called the Working Conditions Survey (1977-1984)

Source see appendix 1

3.1.2 Organisation and funding

Table 3.2 gives an overview of the organisers and funders of the surveys. This information was not always easy to find and sources contradict each other frequently (which can often also be linked to translation errors for the original language to English). In addition, funders or organisers sometimes change throughout the life cycle of a survey. Some cofunders for example are only involved in one specific edition of a survey.

4 These previous editions/precessors of the WEHD will be included in the discussion since some changes and evolutions in the survey can be of relevance.

5 This precessor of the SLOSH will be included in the discussion since some changes and evolutions in the survey can be of relevance.

The majority of the surveys are funded by a governmental institution (department, ministry, etc.). The studies are often carried out and/or organised by (national) research institutes. Also governmental-funded institutes and statistical offices are also often involved in organising these surveys. In some cases, EU (co)funding is provided for the survey.

Further we can also notice that the organisation of a survey is more often done by only one institute than as cooperation between different instances. The funding of the survey, however, is more often a cooperation of different governmental instances and other institutions. In addition we see that it is very rare that the same institution organises and executes the survey as well as fully funds the survey (3 surveys). In most surveys, the funding institutions are not involved in the organisation and execution of the survey (10 surveys). In four of the surveys, the organiser of the survey is also one of the funders, but not the only funder.

Table 3.2 Organising institute/organisation and type of fundings of survey

Country	Survey	Organised by/carried out by	Type	Funded by	Type
AT	AOHM	Institute for Empirical Social Research (IFES)	R	Upper Austrian Chamber of Labour/AK (arbeitskammer)	G
AT	AI	IFES Institute for social research and analysis (SORA)	R	AK (arbeitskammer)	G
BG	NWCS BG	Balkan institute for labour and social policy (BAD) Gesundheitsvorsorge und sicherheitstechnik (GmbH) Scientific and research centre at Sofia University, St Kliment Ohridski	R Ra	General Labour Inspectorate of Bulgaria support of Operational Programme 'Human Resources Development' cofinanced by the European Social Fund of the EU	G EU
DK	WEHD	National Research Centre for the Working Environment (NRCWE)	Rg	NRCWE	Rg
DK	WEC/DW ECS	<i>NRCWE, formerly the National Institute of Occupational Health</i>	Rg	<i>NRCWE</i>	Rg
FI	FNWHS	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health (FIOH)	Gf	Ministry of social affairs and health FIOH	G Gf
FI	FQWLS	Statistics Finland	S	Ministry of Employment and Economy (MEE) Ministry of Social Affairs and Health Finnish Work Environment Fund State Treasury Finnish Institute of Occupational Health Finnish Centre for Pensions Local Government Pensions Institution Centre for Occupational Safety Social Insurance Institution Finnish rehabilitation Foundation	G Gf
FI	WLB	MEE	G	MEE	G
FR	SUMER	Directorate for Research, Studies and Statistics (Dares) General Directorate of labour (DGT)	G	DGT General Directorate of Administration and the Public Sector (DGAFP)	G Gf

Country	Survey	Organised by/carried out by	Type	Funded by	Type
FR	CT	Dares INSEE	G	DGT Dares (Ministry of Work, Employment, Vocational Train- ing and Social Dialogue) DGAFP	G Gf
DE	BIBB/BAu A	1998/99-2011/12: BIBB & Fed- eral Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (BAuA) 2006 & 2012: data collection by TNS Infratest Sozialforschung 1979-1991/92: <i>Federal Institute for Vocational Training Affairs (BIBB)</i> & <i>Institute for Employment Research (LAB)</i>	G Gf R	Federal ministry of education and research	G
IT	ISFOL PLUS	The institute for the Develop- ment of vocational Training of Workers (ISFOL)	G	Ministry of labour European social fund (ESF)	G EU
IT	ISFOL QWS	ISFOL	G	ESF	EU
NL	NEA	TNO Work and employment and Statistics Netherlands CBS (central statistical office)	R S	Ministry of social affairs and employment (SZW)	G
NO	LKU	Statistics Norway (SSB)	S	Arbeids – og inkluderingsdepar- tementet (AID) Statens instituttet for arbeids- miljøforskning (STAMI)	G Rg
ES	ENCT	INSHT under the auspices of the Ministry of Employment and social secu- rity	G	Spanish Ministry of employment and Social Security	G
ES	ECVT	Spanish Ministry of Labour and Social security	G	Spanish Ministry of Labour and Social security	G
SE	SLOSH	Stress Research Institute (Stress- forskningsinstituttet) part of Stockholm University	Ra	Swedish Council for Working Life and Social Research (FAS) Swedish Research Council (VR)	G Gf
SE	SWES	<i>Swedish Work Environment Authority (AV)</i>	G	<i>AV</i> <i>Statistics Sweden (SCB)</i> <i>Ministry of employment of the Swedish government</i>	S Gf G

* G = Governmental
Gf = Governmental funded institute/organisation
S = Statistical office
R= research institute
Rg = Governmental funded Research Institute/organisation
Ra = Academic/Independent Research institute/organisation
EU = funded by the EU
Source see appendix 1

3.2 Survey methodology

3.2.1 Timing and frequency

Table 3.3 gives an overview of the editions of each survey, whether and when next editions are planned and the frequency of the surveys.

The frequency of the surveys varies between quarterly (two Austrian surveys) and every seven years (4 surveys). Other survey frequencies are organised annually (3 surveys), biennial (3 surveys), every 3 to 4 years (4 survey) and every 4 years (2 surveys). One survey is done on a variable frequency (between 2 and 5 years). Of the NCWS BG the frequency is still unknown since a next edition is not yet planned. A long timespan between two subsequent surveys (up to 7 years) is not problematic for working conditions surveys. Working conditions appear to change slowly, so a longer time period is useful to be able to capture changes in these working conditions.

From the surveys, one (the EVCT) has ended and no next edition will be done. Some others are continued in a new version of the survey. From four of the surveys it is unknown whether a next edition of the survey will take place and when this will be. For the other twelve surveys a next edition is already planned or while most probably be done.

Table 3.3 Timing, frequency and periodicity of the surveys

Country	Survey	First edition	Editions	Latest edition	Next edition	Frequency
AT	AOHM	2006	Every 4 months	2014/1	2014/2	Quarterly
AT	AI	1997/1	Every 4 months	2014/3	2014/4	Quarterly
BG	NWCS BG	2010-2011			Unknown	
DK	WEHD	2012			2014 (until 2020)	every 2 years
DK	WEC	1990		1995	Ended – name changed to DWECs	every 5 years
FI	DWECs	2000	2005	2010	Ended – followed by WEHD	every 5 years
FI	FNWHS	1990	1997, 2000, 2003, 2006, 2009	2012	likely in 2015	every 3 years
FI	FQWLS	1977	1984, 1990, 1997, 2003, 2008	2013	Unknown	1977-2003: every 7 years 2003 - every 5 years
FR	WLB	1992 (October)	1993, 1994, 1995, 1996, 1997, 1998, 1999, 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004, 2005, 2006, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012	2013	2014	Annual
FR	SUMER	1987	1994, 2003	2010	2017	More or less every 7 years
DE	CT	1978	1984, 1991, 1998, 2005	2013	Probably 2020	Every 7 years complementing l'enquête Emploi (de l'Insee)
IT	BIBB/BAuA	1979	1985/86, 1991/92, 1998/99, 2005/06	2011/12	2017/2018	Variable: every 6/7 years
IT	ISFOL PLUS	2004 (pre-test survey without a section on quality of work, with almost 10 000 interviews)	2005, 2006, 2008, 2010, 2011	2013		Every 1 to 2 years

Country	Survey	First edition	Editions	Latest edition	Next edition	Frequency
NL	ISFOL QWS	2002	2006	2010	2014	Every 4 years
NO	NEA	2003	2005, 2006, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012	2013	2014	Annual
ES	<i>NEA-cohort</i>	2007	2008	2009	<i>ended</i>	<i>Annual</i>
ES	LKU	1989	1993, 1997, 2000, 2003, 2006	2009		Module included every 3/4 years
SE	ENCT	1987	1993, 1997, 1999, 2004, 2007	2011	2015	Variable: more or less every 4 years
SE	ECVT	1999	2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004, 2006, 2007, 2008, 2009	2010	Ended	Annual – not in 2005
SE	SLOSH	2006	2008, 2010	2012	2014	Every 2 years
SE	<i>SWES</i>	1989	1991, 1993, 1995, 1997, 1999, 2001, 2003, 2004, 2005, 2007	2007	<i>Ended – replaced by SLOSH</i>	<i>Every 2 years</i>

Source see appendix 1

Some surveys have a very long tradition, with three surveys going back into the Seventies. Three other surveys started in the '80 and four in the '90. Only five of the surveys here discussed started after 2000 (and have no predecessor). Further, two surveys which started after 2000 are continuations of surveys started in 1989 or 1990.

This long tradition that exists in most of the surveys provides us with rich and large data sets over a long period of time and enables researchers to monitor changes in working conditions over time. However, this might also impact the surveys for example in terms of methodology, items included, topics addressed, etc. Once a survey is running, it is a difficult exercise to balance between adding new items and changing items in your survey to improve the survey and keep it up to date on the one hand, and keeping items stable in the survey to ensure comparability over time on the other hand.

3.2.2 Survey population

The vast majority of the surveys (11) focus on people in employment. The exact definition of this group sometimes differs. Self-employed are in some cases excluded out of the survey, as well as other atypical, hard-to-cover groups (such as public sector, temporary workers, foreign workers, unemployed, family workers, students, apprentices, etc.). In some surveys, specific questions for either employees or self-employed are included. The base population of regular wage earners, however, is always included.

Table 3.4 gives a detailed overview of the target population of each survey as well as specific exclusion criteria. In some surveys the people 'in employment' are defined as someone who has worked (in a paid job) more than 10 hours in that week. Other definitions are also used.

Table 3.4 Survey population

Country	Survey	Territorial scope	Economic activities	Population	Age	Excluded	Population size
AT	AOHM	national		Employees	older than 16		
AT	AI	national	all	Employed persons	15 and older	self-employed	
BG	NWCS BG	national	all sectors according to NACE 2008	employees working in companies with 6 or more employees			2279565 employees working in 63335 companies
DK	WEHD	national	all	Danish active population who are employed or self-employed	18-64		
DK	WEC/DWECS	national	all	<i>employment status: employees, self-employed and unemployed + residence in Denmark</i>	18-59		
FI	FNWHS	national	all	employees and self-employed who were working at the time of the study- Finnish speaking	20-68		2800861
FI	FQWLS	national	all	employment status: employees who normally work at least 10 hours per week	15-64	not include workers with summer jobs (selected in March/April already)	2 million
FI	WLB	national	all	employees who work at least 10 hours a week	18-64		2146000
FR	SUMER	metropolitan France + overseas department of Reunion (since 2010)	companies covered by the general scheme of French occupational medicine regulation (whole private sector + most public hospital + state-owned company + large parts of public administration)	wage earners monitored by the occupational physician			22 million
FR	CT	national + four overseas departments (since 2013)	private and public sector	employees		Excluded are some temporary construction workers, youth, foreigners in unemployment, workers in hospitality, schools and hotels	21,7 million/90% of workforce

Country	Survey	Territorial scope	Economic activities	Population	Age	Excluded	Population size
DE	BIBB-BAuA	national	all	employees working in a paid job for at least 9 hours a week) (including working family members, parental leave, ...)	15 years and older	apprentices in vocational training, students, people with internships - changes in region included over time	34 million
IT	ISFOL PLUS	national	all		18-75		44 million
IT	ISFOL QWS	national	all	employed population	older than 16		23 million
NL	NEA	national		employees (including self-employed as second occupation)	15-64	self-employed	
NO	LKU	national	all	individuals-persons in Norway	16 and older		
ES	ENCT	Spain except for Ceuta, Melilla, Spanish territories in Northern Africa)	all	working population: employees and self-employed	16 and older	cities of Ceuta and Melilla	
ES	ECVT	Spain except for Ceuta, Melilla, Spanish territories in Northern Africa)	all	working population: employees and self-employed	16 and older	cities of Ceuta and Melilla	
SE	SLOSH	national	all		19-74		
SE	SWEES	national	all	employed population	16-64		4,6 million

Source see appendix 1

The upper age limit of the target population in general is 64 or 65 years, with exception of cohort studies which keep participants in the sample after they have passed the age limit (f.e. the sample of the SLOSH contains participants up to age 74). Often the age limit of 64 years is not strictly treated, meaning that older employees, who participate in the survey, are not removed from the data. However, these people older than 64 years are not targeted within the survey. Regarding the lower age limit of the target population less consensus can be found. Rather often the age of either 15 or 16 years is treated as lower limit. The differences in the preference for age 15 or 16 are country linked and can also be found in the EWCS, for which the lower age limit varies across countries between 15 and 16 years. The variance in these age limit might be linked to the country specific age on which people might enter the labour market. In a few surveys, a higher limit is used. For the two Spanish surveys the lower limit is 17 years. One Finnish survey (WLB) uses the limit of 18 years and another even 25 years (Finnish National Work and Health Survey). In general, however, it can be concluded that all the surveys aim to target the working population, which in general is between the age of 15 and 64.

3.2.3 Survey design

Two very common methods of survey design in social sciences are cross-sectional studies and longitudinal surveys. A cross-sectional survey collects data of a sample of the population at one specific moment in time. Various waves of a survey always include a new sample of the population. This implies that it is less evident to investigate causal relations and that the focus is more on the prevalence of specific concepts at a specific moment in time. In a longitudinal survey, the same subset or sample of the population is followed and surveyed over time. This enables researchers to investigate trends and look better for causal relations. A cohort study is a specific type of a longitudinal study, in which a subsample of the population, which is homogeneous for example in terms of age, is studied over time. With a cohort study, subsets of the population can be followed and some characteristics can be studied as the cohort ages over time (Levin, 2005, 2006a, 2006b; Mann, 2003).

Twelve of the surveys have a cross-sectional design (Table 3.5). The other five surveys combine a cross-sectional design with one or more cohorts or panels included in the sample. The WEHD is a continuation of the DWECS, which followed several cohorts. These cohorts are included in the WEDH and complemented with new subsamples. In the NEA, a cohort was followed between 2007 and 2009 as a part of the total sample. Besides this, the design is cross-sectional.

This leads to the conclusion that only two Nordic countries have a large scale panel survey on working conditions (e.g. Denmark and Sweden). The Italian ISFOL PLUS survey has also a cohort approach, but is rather limited in its scope (see *infra*).

Table 3.5 Survey design

Country	Survey	CS/LT/CO	Methodology remarks
AT	AOHM	CS	
AT	AI	CS	Online interface available since 2006.
BG	NWCS BG	CS	
DK DK	WEHD WEC/DWECS	CS & CO CS & CO	Cohort included <i>The WEC baseline cohort of 1990 was followed in 1995 and 2000 and the sample was in each round supplemented with 18-22 year old persons and immigrants. The DWECS is an extension of the WEC. DWECS was a split panel survey and comprised a follow-up study of a sample of employees interviewed in 1990 and again in 1995. Partially overlapping this panel was a panel of employees interviewed in 1995 and again in 2000. At the same time, the study comprised three cross-sectional surveys from 1990, 1995 and 2000, of comparable samples of employees in Denmark. Thus the study had a design that enabled both surveillance of the overall work environment and follow-up studies of occupational exposures and subsequent health outcomes.</i>
FI	FNWHS	CS	
FI	FQWLS	CS	Since 2000 connections to EWCS have been strengthened
FI	WLB	CS	Trend/repeated cross-section
FR	SUMER	CS	Since 2003: next to interview with physician, an auto questionnaire filled in before visit to physician. Due to limited voluntary participation of physicians in 2010 a set of involuntary physicians were explicitly requested to participate.
FR	CT	CS	Addition to LFS: continuous data collection: every week
DE	BIBB/BAuA	LT (trends)	Retrospective information on individuals achievement process Involvement of BAuA resulted in a stronger focus on working conditions and their outcomes.
IT	ISFOL PLUS	CS & CO	
IT	ISFOL QWS	CS	The questionnaire has been enlarged compared to the 2006 wave
NL	NEA	CS& CO	NEA-Cohort within cross-sectional design
NO	LKU	CS & panel	In 1996 a new system for surveys related to level of living was introduced, with a cross-sectional survey and a panel survey focused on health, residence and work. In the panel study it is desirable to keep the cross-sectional qualities in the sample in order to make sure that the sample is representative for the population that the survey is supposed to cover.
ES	ENCT	CS	2007 = turning point
ES	ECVT	CS	Occasional survey
SE SE	SLOSH SWES	CO CS	Items of the questionnaire consist partly of questions from the SWES. <i>Long-term study of random or different samples</i> <i>Survey in addition of the LFS for a subsample (10-15 000): after completing the LFS, the interview of the SWES follows.</i>

Source see appendix 1

3.3 Data collection and survey questionnaire

3.3.1 Mode of data collection

Several data collection methods can be used when a survey is done (Couper, 2011; Groves et al., 2004; Roberts, 2007):

- *CAPI/PAPI*: computer assisted personal interview/paper assisted personal interview: this is a face-to-face interview between the participant and interviewer;
- *CATI/PATI*: computer assisted telephone interview/paper assisted telephone interview: the participant is contacted by telephone and the survey/interview is done by telephone. There is no face to face contact between the participant and interviewer;

- *CAWI*: computer assisted web interview: this is the typical web survey, which can be done by the participant either at his/her own computer at home, or at a specific pc-lab provided by the researchers. There is no direct contact or interaction between the participant and researcher;
- *Self-Administered Questionnaire (SAQ)*: in this case the participant receives the questionnaire and has to complete the questionnaire him/herself. There is no interviewer coding the answers of the participant immediately. Auto questionnaires can be given to participants in specific setting, send to the participants' home (by mail) with an envelope to return the questionnaire, or a web link sent by email (or mail) to the participants;
- *Mixed method*: in this case participants are offered several possibilities to complete the survey. For example in the NEA the participant can complete the paper questionnaire and return it by mail, or follow a link and fill in a web survey, or contact a helpdesk and fill in the questionnaire through a telephone interview.

There is much variety regarding to the data collection methods used. Recently, all computer assisted methods (CATI, CAPI and CAWI) are becoming the most popular survey methods. We can see that the surveys often change methods throughout time, following technology, time preference, etc. Surveys with a longer tradition (starting in the '70 and '80) often started off as face-to-face (PAPI) interviews, now turning more and more to telephone interviews (CATI) or web surveys (CAWI). Postal questionnaires nowadays are mostly sent with a link to the web survey, offering participant both options to choose from. Further, several surveys use a mix of different methods (f.e. CATI as primary method, CAPI when the person cannot be reached by telephone and SAQ in addition to the interview) to be able to cover the target population as well as possible and limit selection bias. Table 3.6 gives an overview of all the data collection methods used for the surveys as well as changes over time in these methods.

The interviews (CATI/CAPI) are mostly done at the home of the respondent (or a location of choice). Only one survey, the NWCS BG is done at the enterprise of the respondent. The SUMER is done during a visit to an occupational physician, at his/her office. The preference is often given to administering the survey outside of the workplace to avoid interference of the workplace situation and to ensure that respondents can answer the questions freely.

In a few methodological reports of surveys, information is provided about the duration of the interview or time needed for participants to complete the questionnaire. There are large differences in this time use, varying between 22 minutes and more than 1 hour.

Table 3.6 Data collection method

Country	Survey	Mode of data collection	Method	Location	Average duration
AT	AOHM	Face to face interviews	CAPI, PAPI		
AT	AI	Face-to-face interviews	CAPI, PAPI		
BG	NWCS BG	Face-to-face interviews, online surveys, mail questionnaires, focus groups, data from enterprises, administrative data	Mixed method	At the enterprise	30-60 minutes
DK	WEHD	Web survey	SAQ (web + postal)	Postal invitation with link to web survey	
DK	WEC/DWECS	<i>Postal questionnaires (telephone interviews as second alternative for initial non responders) + possibility to fill in questionnaire on the web</i>	<i>SAQ</i>	<i>At home</i>	<i>45 minutes</i>
FI	FNWHS	By telephone (personal interviewing as second alternative)	CATI (and CAPI)	At home	31 minutes
FI	FQWLS	Face-to-face interviews	PAPI, CAPI	Mostly at respondents home, sometimes at place of work, or at library or cafeteria	66 minutes
FI	WLB	By telephone	CATI	At home	22 minutes
FR	SUMER	Auto questionnaire (paper & pen) + face to face questionnaire filled in by occupational physician	Mixed method: PAPI/CAPI & SAQ	At practice of physician	
FR	CT	2 CAPI and 4 CATI	CAPI & CATI		1 hour for 1 person, 1 hour 45 minutes for 2 persons
DE	BIBB-BAuA	CAPI until 1998/1999, since 2005/2006 CATI	CATI	At home	40 minutes
IT	ISFOL PLUS		CATI	At home	Average 22 minutes
IT	ISFOL QWS		CATI	At home	No information, but duration of 25 minutes has been planned
NL	NEA	Mixed-mode: PAPI, CAWI + possibility of telephone interview	Mixed method= PAPI & CAWI (+CATI)		Around 20 minutes
NO	LKU	Telephone interview	CATI	By telephone	
ES	ENCT	Face-to-face interviews	CAPI, PAPI, TAWI	At home	27,1 minutes
ES	ECVT	By phone, CAPI when not possible to contact by phone	CATI (CAPI)	By telephone	
SE	SLOSH	Registries + SAQ	Registry + SAQ		
SE	SWES	<i>Telephone interview + questionnaire</i>	<i>Mixed: CATI + SAQ</i>	<i>By telephone</i>	

Source see appendix 1

3.3.2 Survey questionnaire

It is more difficult to find details on the questionnaires of the surveys. Only some (10) of the questionnaires are publicly available and often only in the language of the country (and not in English) which makes it difficult to consult the questionnaires. We can notice that there is no consistent trend in the length of the surveys or the number of questions included. This varies between 25 questions and more than 280 questions. Table 3.7 gives an overview of the available information about the questionnaires of the surveys.

Table 3.7 Survey questionnaire

Country	Survey	Number of questions	Language	Available	Remarks
AT	AOHM				
AT	AI	26 + 30 questions on working conditions + background information		Not publicly	Expanded and revised several times
BG	NWCS BG	> 200		Not publicly	Three questionnaires: show cars for face-to-face interviews, online and paper (postal)
DK DK	WEHD WEC/DWEC/S	55 +/- 220	Danish Danish	Yes	
FI	FNWHS	200	Finnish, Swedish	Yes (Finnish version)	
FI	FQWLS	>160	Finnish, English	Yes (version 2003)	Similar questions have been used over all waves resulting in large comparability over time
FI	WLB		Finnish	Yes	Updated in 2012 (technical and content)
FR	SUMER	153 in questionnaire for medical officers + 70 in questionnaire for respondents	French	Yes	
FR	CT	80 + some sub-questions	French	Yes	Employee and employers questionnaire some differences across waves
DE	BIBB-BAuA	600	German	Yes	No English version available for participants. Some translations available for certain topics.
IT	ISFOL PLUS	280 questions, in 4 sections	Italian	Yes	Extended with section on competences
IT	ISFOL QWS	108 questions and 27 sub-questions	Italian		Enlarged since 2006 Limited differences for employees and self-employed
NL	NEA	130	Dutch	Yes	
NO	LKU				
ES	ENCT	62	Spanish	Yes	Adaptations each year
ES	ECVT	101	Spanish	Yes	
SE SE	SLOSH SWES	25		Yes	

Source see appendix 1

3.4 Survey sample and response

3.4.1 Survey sample

Survey samples can be designed and extracted in several ways, which can impact the sampling error. Therefore it is important to know what the sampling frame, sampling method and sample size of a survey was before using its data.

Across the 17 examined surveys, four common sampling methods are used (Table 3.8). The first and most used sampling method is simple random sampling (SRS). With this method, each element (and subset) is assigned an equal probability to be selected (Groves et al., 2004). This method is used by seven of the surveys. A second method that is commonly used is stratified random sampling. Here, the population is divided into separate and exclusive sub groups or strata, which are treated as independent sub-populations. From each of these subgroups, a separate sample is randomly drawn (f.e. using SRS) (Groves et al., 2004). This method meets the most important criticism to SRS, namely that it might not represent the makeup of the population. Using stratified random sampling one can assure the different subgroups in the population are all represented in the sample. From the selected surveys, five surveys use the stratified random sampling method. The third method, which is used in four of the selected surveys, is multistage clustered sampling. In clustered sampling, the elements are not selected separately, but groups of elements are selected. This method is mostly used in a multi-stage method, in which different steps are taken to identify clusters and select elements in these clusters. Finally, one of the surveys, the NEA, uses the systematic probability proportional to size method. With this method, the probability of an element being selected varies across items and is proportional to the size measure which is included (Groves et al., 2004).

Table 3.8 Sampling method

Simple Random Sampling	Stratified Random Sampling	Multistage Clustered Sampling	Systematic Probability Proportional to Size
FNWHS	WEHD (<i>WEC, DWECs</i>)	AOHM	NEA (<i>NEA-cohort</i>)
FQWLS	CT	AI	
WLB	ENCT	NWCS BG (2-stage)	
SUMER	ECVT	ISFOL QWS (3-stage)	
BIBB-BAuA	SLOSH (<i>SWES</i>)		
LKU	ISFOL PLUS		

Source see appendix 1

Table 3.9 gives more detailed information about the sampling method, sampling frame and the sample size of the last edition of the survey. It was not possible to collect information about the sampling frame and sample size of each of the surveys. However, some interesting aspects should be highlighted here.

In most cases, the sampling frame of the surveys is a central or population registry. Other surveys take the national Labour Force Survey (LFS) sample as sampling frame, or a population census. Others again use a more specific sampling frame (f.e. ADM-master sample, sample extracted from telephone data files, etc.).

The size of the sample of the last editions of the surveys varies widely between 2500 and 80000. Also across editions, there are often differences in the sample size. Further we should also note that the sample size is only the starting point of the survey and that the final net response not only depends on the sample size.

Table 3.9 Sampling method, sampling frame and sample size

Country	Survey	Sampling frame	Sampling method	Sample size last edition
AT	AOHM		Stratified multi-stage clustered random sample	1,000/quarter
AT	AI	Central registry	Stratified multi-stage clustered random sampling	900/quarter = 3,600/year
BG	NWCS BG		Two-stage cluster sampling with probability proportional to the size of	2,500
DK	WEHD	Each year a new sample	2 subsamples: 1 randomly selected, 1 selected to represent 1000 workplaces	35,000+15,000
DK	DWECs	<i>Central population registry: follow-up sample + additional samples (age, migration, industry, job specific)</i>	<i>Stratified Simple random sampling design with proportional allocation + follow up respondents in cohort</i>	30,000
FI	FNWHS	Finnish population census	Simple random sample	5,000
FI	FQWLS	Sample taken from monthly LFS sample	Simple random sample	6,499 (3,000 to 6,500 in each round)
FI	WLB	Register of statistics Finland	Simple random sample	
FR	SUMER	Those visiting the physician + in selected group (not excluded) + willing to participate	Random sample of chartered medical officers -examined employees	53,940
FR	CT	Taken from the LFS sample: whole population except those living in institutions, based on list of dwellings from fiscal data	Stratified samples: mainland France +overseas departments + public service and healthcare establishments	27,000+4,000+6,000
DE	BIBB/BAuA	Register used: ADM-master sample of precincts (Micro census for controlling and weighting)	Random sample	317,980
IT	ISFOL PLUS	Extracted from telephone data files	Stratified random sampling - complex survey - 9 sub-samples	
IT	ISFOL QWS		Three stage sampling	5,000
NL	NEA	Municipality population register	Systematic Probability Proportional to Size - sample	80,000
NO	LKU	Bereg1	Random sample + cohort	20,460
ES	ENCT	Taken from municipality register	Stratified sample	8,892
ES	ECVT	Taken from municipality register	Stratified sampling	
SE	SLOSH	Sample consists of all participants of SWES 2003 and 2005 + part of SWES 2007	Cohort	21,489
SE	SWES	<i>Population register</i>	<i>Stratified random sampling</i>	14,000

Source see appendix 1

3.4.2 Response

For most surveys either the gross response or net response is reported. The response differs largely across the surveys and is dependent on the initial sample size. Therefore the response rate is more useful to compare across surveys (Table 3.10).

The response rates (when reported) vary between 30% and 89%, which is a large difference. The differences can partially be linked to the method of data collection. For example in the SUMER, which has a response rate of 89%, the respondents are requested to participate to the survey during

their obligatory visit to the occupational physician. The interview is done by the physician during the visit. This set up is more likely to enhance people to participate in a survey than when they receive a questionnaire at home by mail and have to fill it in and return it themselves (which is the case f.e. in the NEA).

However, in several surveys specific actions are taken to enhance the people to participate and limit the response rate. Reminders are frequently sent when people have not yet responded after a certain time. In some cases non-responders are contacted by telephone to request participation, copies of the survey are sent to the participant, telephone interviews are conducted, etc.

Table 3.10 Gross and net response and response rate

Country	Survey	Gross response	Net response	Response rate
AT	AOHM		8,954	
AT	AI		900/quarter	
BG	NWCS BG			85.50%
DK	WEHD		16,300+15,000	51%
DK	WEC/DWECs		14,453	53%
FI	FNWHS		8,363	40%
FI	FQWLS		4,392	68%
FI	WLB		2,004	77.40%
FR	SUMER	53,940	47,983	89% (of which 97% also filled in questionnaire)
FR	CT	>30,000		
DE	BIBB-BAuA	54,152	20,036	44.30% of sample
IT	ISFOL PLUS		55,000	
IT	ISFOL QWS	5,000		
NL	NEA	24,480	23,303	Brut: 32.6%, net: 30.6%
NO	LKU		12,255	59.90%
ES	ENCT		8,892	39.9%
ES	ECVT		9,240	
SE	SLOSH		17,409	56.80% (proportion of sample employed in 2012 = 74%)
SE	SWES	16,000		

Source see appendix 1

3.5 Scope of survey

3.5.1 Objectives of the survey

The main themes of these surveys are all related to working conditions, occupational health issues and work-related health, job satisfaction and other work-related attitudes. However, the surveys each have their own focus. Some surveys cover on a broad range of issues, while other focus on particular issues. Survey such as the FNWHS, SLOSH or NEA have a broad scope, including all aspect related to working conditions, health and work-related health issues, job satisfaction and other work-related attitudes. On the other hand, the SUMER for example strongly focusses on mapping the exposure of workers to occupational risks. The AOHM is also clearly directed towards the monitoring of work-related health. The main themes addressed in the surveys are summarised in Table 3.11.

Next to these dominant themes, Table 3.12 gives an overview of the purposes of the surveys. The main and most prevalent purpose of the surveys is to map the up-to-date state of affairs on these topics, often combined with monitoring the changes over time (using the different waves of the survey) and looking for trends. For example the SUMER aims to give an up-to-date view of workers exposition to pressures and nefast health conditions at work. The ECVT documents the current life quality at work in Spain. Other surveys clearly focus on monitoring changes. The WLB measures changes in the quality of Finnish working life, the WEHD is developed to assess whether the working environment improves as expected over time. The AI wants to diagnose changes in the working

environment and long-term developments. The FQWLS at last aims to monitor both working conditions at that point in time and the changes in them over time.

Table 3.11 Overview of themes addressed by surveys

Country	Survey	Working conditions	Changes in working conditions	Health, health care, lifestyle habits	Work-related health - aetiology - relationship work and health	Job satisfaction & job attitudes
AT	AOHM				*	
AT	AI	*	*		*	*
BG	NWCS BG	*				
DK	WEHD	*	*	*	*	
DK	WEC/DWECS	*	*	*	*	
FI	FNWHS	*		*	*	*
FI	FQWLS	*	*			
FI	WLB	*				*
FR	SUMER	*		*	*	
FR	CT	*				
DE	BIBB-BAuA	*	*			*
IT	ISFOL PLUS	*				
IT	ISFOL QWS	*				
NL	NEA	*	*		*	
NO	LKU	*				
ES	ENCT	*				*
ES	ECVT	*			*	*
SE	SLOSH	*		*	*	
SE	SWES	*		*	*	

Source see appendix 1

In addition to this monitoring, some surveys - such as the WEHD (and WEC/DWECS in earlier waves), BIBB-BAuA, NEA, SLOSH - also aim to gain insight in the aetiology of changes in health and/or labour market status, related to working conditions, occupational risk factors, etc.

Further, some of the surveys have the purpose to provide input to policy makers or serve as input for policy decisions. This input either can be related to a specific policy decision or programme (WEHD: evaluate improvements in light of national working environment strategy2020; ISFOL PLUS: support proposal of classification of occupations related to occupational risks) or can provide input to related policy activities and decisions in general (FNWHS: input for public debate; SUMER: confront current situation with regulations; NEA: provide reference data for the purpose of occupational health and safety covenants).

In addition, two of the surveys also explicitly aim to provide input to research. FQWLS want to provide input or research related to working conditions. The SUMER aims to serve as a reference point for researcher to determine future research priorities. Table 3.13 bundles the brief objectives (themes covered, purpose/goal of survey) of each of the surveys.

Table 3.12 Overview of main purposes of surveys

Country	Survey	Monitoring	Up-to-data picture	Picture of changes and evolution, trends	Understanding aetiology health problems	Input for policy	Input for research related to working conditions
AT	AOHM	*	*				
AT	AI	*	*	*			
BG	NWCS BG					*	
DK	WEHD	*			*	*	
DK	WEC/DWECs	*			*		
FI	FNWHS	*					
FI	FQWLS	*	*			*	*
FI	WLB	*	*	*			
FR	SUMER	*	*			*	*
FR	CT	*	*	*			
DE	BIBB-BAuA				*		
IT	ISFOL PLUS						
IT	ISFOL QWS	*					
NL	NEA				*	*	
NO	LKU	*	*				
ES	ENCT		*				
ES	ECVT		*				
SE	SLOSH	*	*	*	*		
SE	SWES	*	*	*	*		

Source see appendix 1

Table 3.13 Objectives of surveys

Country	Survey	Objectives
AT	AOHM	The objective is to be a representative quantitative survey focusing on the work-related health of employees.
AT	AI	The objective of the Austrian Work Climate Index is to diagnose changes in the working environment and long-term developments before they can be detected in 'hard' economic indicators. The consequences of economic changes and developments on the subjective experience of employees can be summarised in a measured value that is an addition to established indicators. Due to its frequent waves, the AI allows for the observation of long-term structural developments in employment structure and work organisation, such as an increase in precarious employment, bogus self-employment and changes in working time.
BG	NWCS BG	The objectives are: To collect and analyse data about working conditions in enterprises in all economic sectors in Bulgaria. To support a proposal for a classification of the economic sectors according to the degree of risk for each of the following topics: nature of work, working environment, work organisation, working hours, work and health, pay, information and consultations, discrimination and violence, and work and non-working life. This will serve to determine the most hazardous sectors in the economy. To provide general conclusions and recommendations for policies on working conditions.
DK	WEHD	The objectives are: Surveillance: surveillance of the working population to monitor the prevalence of occupational risk factors and the prevalence and incidence of health symptoms. Aetiology: estimating changes in health and labour market status as possible consequences of occupational risk factors. The results will be used to assess whether the working environment improves as expected according to the National Working Environment Strategy 2020.
DK	WEC	<i>Set up as surveillance programme.</i> <i>The objectives of WEC are: Surveillance of the working population, monitoring:</i> <i>prevalence of occupational risk factors</i> <i>prevalence and incidence of health symptoms</i> <i>lifestyle and habits</i> <i>Aim is to estimate changes of health and labour market status as possible consequences of occupational risk factors.</i>

Country	Survey	Objectives
FI	DWECS	<p><i>The objectives are:</i></p> <p><i>Surveillance: surveillance of the working population to monitor the prevalence of occupational risk factors and the prevalence and incidence of health symptoms.</i></p> <p><i>Aetiology: estimating changes in health and labour market status as possible consequences of occupational risk factors.</i></p> <p><i>The results will be used to assess whether the working environment improves as expected according to the National Working Environment Strategy 2020.</i></p> <p><i>The objective is to describe working conditions, health and lifestyle in a cohort consisting of Danish workers (1 to 400 workers). DWECS makes it possible to:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1) Carry out cross-sectional analyses of the prevalence of work environmental exposures and health effects among various groups</i> <i>2) Carry out follow-up studies of the association between work environmental exposures and health and labour market effects.</i>
FI	FNWHS	<p>The survey serves as a national surveillance system on perceived working conditions (physical work environment, physical and mental workload), organisational factors at work, work climate, gender and age equality, vocational skills, job satisfaction, perceived health and work ability, health-related behaviour, reconciliation of work and family life, and the functioning of occupational health services.</p> <p>The survey aims to collect information on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working conditions and other work related factors Health, well-being and work ability of working population Health related lifestyle factors Use of health care services Functioning of occupational health services
FI	FQWLS	<p>The objective of the Quality of Work Life Surveys (FQWLS) has been to produce data on the state of working life to support labour policy decisions and the development of work organisation, to monitor employees' working conditions and changes in them.</p> <p>The surveys aim to provide information for public debate about Finnish people's views on their working conditions and about how these conditions have changed. The surveys also supply material for the research, training and communication activities related to working conditions that take place in diverse quarters of society.</p>
FR	WLB	<p>The objective of the WLB is to monitor changes in the quality of Finnish working life from the perspective of employees. For the purposes of the survey, the quality of working life encompasses multiple issues, ranging from job security to intra-staff relationships. The survey provides an up-to-date picture of the quality of work for employees as well information on trends.</p> <p>The annual survey studies employee opinion on the quality of working life in Finland. Main themes are psychosocial working environment, job characteristics, pay systems, satisfaction with the job, employment security, training and development, capacity to work, and bullying and discrimination at work. This survey is planned to complement the FQWLS, but the WLB investigates more the experiences of short-term changes in working conditions.</p>
FR	SUMER	<p>The main objective is to map the exposure of employees to occupational risks in France in order to assess the overall situation and to develop preventive measures for all actors involved in occupational health and safety. Thus the objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better view on current state in terms of exposition to pressures and working in nefast health conditions for prevention workers. Possibility to confront current situation with regulations (hygiene, safety, ...). A reference point for researchers to determine research priorities
DE	CT	<p>The objectives of this survey are to permit detailed analyses of employees' working conditions by socio-professional category and sector of activity. The survey's depth in terms of time also allows trends to be recognised. The survey consists of two sections: the 'In employment' and 'Employers' division allows complementary information to be obtained from employers alongside that gathered from employees.</p>
IT	BIBB-BAuA	<p>The objectives of this survey are to assess work tasks, working conditions, occupation in transition, vocational and further training, acquisition and utilization of vocational qualifications, job satisfaction and the health impact of working conditions on a continuous basis. It focuses on two types of research:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualification research: the association between respondents' (vocational) education and employment. Research on occupations and their change: job activity, skill and task requirements, working conditions and health in the current job.
IT	ISFOL PLUS	<p>The survey aims to integrate the LFS by identifying both formal and substantive characteristics of employment contracts (such as 'bogus' self-employed), including wages and quality of work and employment, and to investigate in detail the labour search process by focusing on the complexity of search chains.</p>
NL	ISFOL QWS	<p>The objectives is to monitor the main indicators in job quality by taking into account the increasing relevance of both nonstandard employment and the service sectors by developing a set of indicators according to several Italian studies on the quality of work. The survey aims to fill a gap on labour market knowledge left uncovered by both Istat LFS and Isfol PLUS.</p>

Country	Survey	Objectives
NO	NEA	The aim of the NWCS is to investigate the quality of work and employment in the Netherlands. The NWCS tracks trends in work risks, the effects of those risks and the measures taken by employers. The NWCS data are also used to analyse the relationship between work and health. We provide employers' organizations, unions and the Ministry of Social affairs and Employment with national reference data for the purpose of occupational health and safety covenants. <i>This longitudinal database (2007-2009) of the NEA is used to give more insight into cause and effect relations.</i>
ES	NEA-cohort	
ES	LKU	The LKU has as its primary objective to, over time, cover all important issues concerning the level of living, including rotating topics, such as working conditions (1996, 2000, 2003, 2006 and 2008).
SE	ENCT	The objective is to research the quality of life of employees in the workplace from two perspectives: by obtaining information about the situations and activities in employees' work and family environments; and by obtaining subjective information about the personal perceptions that workers have about their labour relations and conditions. Thus, this research combines both objective and subjective information.
SE	ECVT	The objective is to provide statistical information on life quality at work in Spain and how Spanish workers perceive their own working conditions. Main goals: Finding out about life quality in the work place for workers (employees and self-employed): situations and activities at work, subjective perception of worker of own working conditions and relationships, and degree of satisfaction in the workplace. Information on labour situations of workers (regarding job, professional career, integration at work and promotion procedures, family structure and situation) since all these factors play a key role in assessing life quality in the workplace. Obtaining socio-economic data of workers in order to relate results to their labour situation.
	SLOSH (SWES)	SLOSH study is a cohort survey with a focus on the association between work organization, work environment and health. SLOSH makes it possible to investigate how work environment factors affect health and wellbeing over time. Primary focus: wide range of prospective longitudinal research questions about relationships between labour market participation, working life, social environment, personal agency, and health. Better understand aetiology of illnesses and functional limitations of public health relevance, - increase understanding of 'causes behind the causes'.

Source see appendix 1; main source: cited from Eurofound (2014a)

3.5.2 Topics covered in the survey

The surveys are selected because they focus on working conditions and occupational health and safety issues. Consequently, these are topics that are covered in the surveys. Table 3.14 gives a general overview of the (subgroups of) topics that are covered in each of the surveys. In Table a1.2 in the appendix a more detailed overview can be found of the topics and aspects covered by the surveys.

Most of the surveys include some questions to cover background information, such as socio-demographic information (age, education, gender, etc.), information about the company (size, sector, characteristics, etc.) or career path of the interviewee (occupational changes, work experience, etc.). In some surveys, these aspects are very detailed document. In other cases, only a few aspects are questioned.

In all surveys, the main core of the survey is devoted to one or several aspects of working conditions. Four surveys clearly focus on occupational safety and health issues (AOHM, SUMER, SLOSH (SWES) and WEHD (WEC/DWECs)). Aspects of the physical and psychosocial work environment are questioned at a detailed level. Further much attention is given to the health of the person, health-related aspects and the work-health relation and in some cases life style habits (such as smoking, alcohol consumption, etc.).

The other thirteen surveys focus more on working conditions in general. With exception of the CT, they all cover the three sub dimensions related to job quality (work organisation, employment conditions and social relations). These surveys tend to cover more different aspects of working conditions and also include questions on job satisfaction or work-related attitudes in the survey.

For work organisation, the most frequently addressed aspects are working time (working hours, unusual working hours, ...), the psychosocial work environment and the physical work environment. The employment conditions are on the one hand covered by looking at wage, contract, etc. and on the other hand by questions about training and development. Not all surveys include both these

aspects in their questionnaire. Social relations are in some cases measured by focussing on participation, representation and voice of the employees. Other surveys devote more attention to relations with managers and colleagues (support, bullying, violence, etc.). Further we notice that most surveys are extended to cover more aspects related to working conditions and the outcomes throughout time and across different waves (and versions of the survey).

Table 3.14 Overview of main topics covered

Country	Survey	Background information	Working conditions	Work organisation	Working time	Work organisation	Autonomy	Work organisation in general	Working life	Team work	Dealing with clients	Work life balance	Psychological work environment	Physical work environment	Employment conditions	Employment conditions	Training and development	Social relations	Outcomes	Job satisfaction and work-related	Health	Life style and habits
AT	AOHM	*	*	*			*			*		*	*	*	*			*	*	*	*	*
AT	AI	*	*	*	*	*						*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
BG	NWCS BG	*	*	*	*	*				*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
DK	WEHD	*	*	*	*	*	*					*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
DK	DWECs	*	*	*	*	*	*					*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
FI	FNWHS	*	*	*	*	*						*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
FI	FQWLS	*	*	*	*	*		*	*	*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
FI	WLB	*	*	*	*	*	*					*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
FR	SUMER	*	*	*	*	*	*			*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
FR	CT	*	*	*	*	*	*			*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
DE	BIBB/BAuA	*	*	*	*	*	*					*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
IT	ISFOL PLUS	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*			*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
IT	ISFOL QWS	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*			*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
NL	NEA	*	*	*	*	*	*					*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
NO	LKU	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
ES	ENCT	*	*	*	*	*	*					*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
ES	ECVT	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
SE	SLOSH	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*			*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
SE	SWES	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*			*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

Source see appendix 1

Table 3.15 Documentation of surveys

Country	Survey	Website	Publications or reports (methodological, technical, ...)	Questionnaire	Data available?
AT	AOHM	http://ooe.arbeiterkammer.at/beratung/arbeitundgesundheitsindex/Waerum_Arbeitsklima_Index.html			
AT	AI	http://ooe.arbeiterkammer.at/beratung/arbeitundgesundheitsindex.html	http://www.db.arbeitsklima.at/	www.arbeitsklima.at	www.arbeitsklima.at
BG	NWCS BG	http://projects.gli.government.bg/index.php?mod=content&show=51	http://www.gli.government.bg/upload/docs/2013-01/doklad_Nacionalno_izsledvane.pdf		
DK	WEHD	http://www.arbejdsmiljoforskning.dk/da/arbejdsmiljoedata/arbejdsmiljoeghelbred-20	http://www.arbejdsmiljoforskning.dk/da/arbejdsmiljoedata/arbejdsmiljoeghelbred-20/arbejdsmiljoeghelbred-2012/resume		
DK	WEC/DWEC	http://www.arbejdsmiljoforskning.dk/da/arbejdsmiljoedata/nak2005	http://www.arbejdsmiljoforskning.dk/da/nyheder/arkiv/2011/~media/Forside/Arbejdsmiljoedata/Arbejdsmiljoeghelbred-2010/Samlet-rapport-Arbejdsmiljoeghelbred-i-DK-2010.pdf		
FI	FNWHS	http://www.ttl.fi/tyojaterveys	http://www.ttl.fi/fi/verkkokirjat/tyoja_terveys_suomessa/Documents/Tyoja_terveys_2009.pdf http://www.ttl.fi/fi/verkkokirjat/tyoja_terveys_suomessa/Documents/Tyoja_Terveys_2012.pdf	http://www.ttl.fi/fi/verkkokirjat/tyoja_terveys_suomessa/Documents/Tyoja_terveys_2009.pdf http://www.ttl.fi/fi/verkkokirjat/tyoja_terveys_suomessa/Documents/Tyoja_Terveys_2012.pdf	FIOH intranet: www.occuphealth.fi/e/
FI	FQWLS	http://www.stat.fi/til/tyoolot/	http://www.stat.fi/tup/julkaisut/tiedostot/isbn_978-952-244-101-0.html http://www.stat.fi/tup/julkaisut/tiedostot/isbn_978-952-244-101-0.html	Lehto & Sutela, 2009 – English version of the questionnaire of 2008 in appendix 2	
FI	WBL	http://www.tem.fi/?s=3893	http://www.tem.fi/files/35605/TEMrap_6_2013.pdf http://www.tem.fi/files/33535/TEMjuli_29_2012_web.pdf	http://www.fsd.uta.fi/en/	http://www.fsd.uta.fi/en/ http://www.fsd.uta.fi/fi/aineistot/luettelo/FSD2824/kuF2824_fin.pdf

Country	Survey	Website	Publications or reports (methodological, technical, ...)	Questionnaire	Data available?
FR	SUMER	http://travail-emploi.gouv.fr/etudes-recherches-statistiques-de,76/statistiques,78/conditions-de-travail-et-sante,80/les-enquetes-surveillance-medicale,1999/	http://travail-emploi.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/Methodologie_de_redressement_des_donnees_Sumer_2010.pdf http://travail-emploi.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/Presentation_detaillee_de_Sumer_2010.pdf http://travail-emploi.gouv.fr/IMG/xls/Les_donnees_sur_les_risques_professionnels_par_sexe_en_2010-2.xls http://travail-emploi.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/Methodologie_de_redressement_des_donnees_Sumer_2010.pdf	http://travail-emploi.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/Questionnaire_Sumer_2010.pdf http://travail-emploi.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/Auto-questionnaire_Sumer_2010.pdf	on request - few tables on website
FR	CT	http://travail-emploi.gouv.fr/etudes-recherches-statistiques-de,76/statistiques,78/conditions-de-travail-et-sante,80/les-enquetes-conditions-de-travail,2000/	http://travail-emploi.gouv.fr/etudes-recherches-statistiques-de,76/statistiques,78/conditions-de-travail-et-sante,80/les-enquetes-conditions-de-travail,2000/	http://travail-emploi.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/Questionnaire_personnes_en_emploi.pdf http://travail-emploi.gouv.fr/etudes-recherches-statistiques-de,76/statistiques,78/conditions-de-travail-et-sante,80/les-enquetes-conditions-de-travail,2000/les-enquetes-conditions-de-travail,189/questionnaires,1736.html	Online tool
DE	BIBB/BAUA	http://www.bibb.de/de/62622.htm http://www.baua.de/de/Informationen-fuer-die-Praxis/Statistiken/Arbeitsbedingungen/Erwerbstaetigenbefragung-2011-2012.html	http://www.baua.de/de/Informationen-fuer-die-Praxis/Statistiken/Arbeitsbedingungen/Erwerbstaetigenbefragung-2011-2012.html Data collection field report 2012: www.bibb.de/de/63182.htm	In methodological documents www.bibb.de/forum/projekte/bibbia/start.htm	All waves: GWA, DFV, SUF www.gesis.org/ZA
IT	ISFOL PLUS	http://www.isfol.it/temi/Lavoro_professioni/mercato-del-lavoro/plus	http://archivio.isfol.it/DocEditor/test/File/2009/Studio%20Isfol/Studio%20Giammatteo%20impaginato_new.pdf http://sbnlo2.cilea.it/bw5ne2/opac.aspx?WEB=ISFI&IDS=19149	http://archivio.isfol.it/DocEditor/test/File/2012/Bandi/Bando%20122PLUS/Allegato%202_Questionario_PLUS%202011.pdf http://isfoloia.isfol.it/bitstream/123456789/240/1/Mandrone%20PLUS%26M-ACAD.ppt	
IT	ISFOL QWS	http://www.isfol.it/temi/Lavoro_professioni/mercato-del-lavoro/indagine-sulla-qualita-del-lavoro-in-italia			

Country	Survey	Website	Publications or reports (methodological, technical, ...)	Questionnaire	Data available?
NL	NEA	http://www.monitorarbeid.tno.nl/data/bronnen/nea	http://www.monitorarbeid.tno.nl/data/bronnen/nea	http://www.monitorarbeid.tno.nl/dynamics/modules/SFIL0100/view.php?fileId=70	http://www.monitorarbeid.tno.nl/cijfers/visualisaties/interactieve-visualisaties1
NO	LKU	http://www.ssb.no/en/arbeid-og-lonn/statistikker/arbmiljo/hvert-3-aaar/2010-06-01?fane=om#content		Online tool	Online tool
ES	ENCT	http://encuestasnacionales.oect.es/	http://encuestasnacionales.oect.es/	http://encuestasnacionales.oect.es/eng/EngeCuestionarios.jsp	http://encuestasnacionales.oect.es/
ES	ECVT	http://www.empleo.gob.es/		http://www.empleo.gob.es/estadisticas/ecvt/Ecvt2010/ANE/Cuestionario.htm	http://www.empleo.gob.es/estadisticas/ecvt/Ecvt2010/index.htm
SE	SLOSH	http://www.stressforskning.su.se/english/slosh		In document: (Kinsten, Stockholms universitet, & Stressforskningsinstitutet, 2007)	Available in English and Swedish – no fee agreement with external researcher – data available for the scientific community.
SE	SWE\$	http://www.av.se/statistik/officiellt/arbetsmiljon_2011.aspx	http://www.av.se/dokument/statistik/officiell_stat/ARBMIL2011.pdf	http://www.av.se/dokument/statistik/officiell_stat/ARBMIL2011.pdf	

Source see appendix 1

3.6 Survey documentation and data

In Table 3.15 the main web links are provided to the website of each of the surveys and when available, links to documentation, questionnaires, publications and the data are included. For most surveys, some kind of related publication can be found, varying from a discussion on the survey in the appendix to extensive methodological and technical reports on the survey. The questionnaires are less often available and can often be found in appendices of publications or methodological reports. Data availability is even less documented. In some cases, an online tool allows the user to do some explorative analysis on the main variables of the survey. For other surveys information is provided on the procedure and requirements to request access to the data.

3.7 Quality control procedures

Quality control procedures are a very broad concept. It includes all the efforts and procedures that researchers put in place throughout the survey life cycle to ensure the quality of the survey, and the accuracy, validity and reliability of the collected data (Gallup Europe, n.d.; Groves et al., 2004; Koch, Blom, Stoop, & Kappelhof, 2009; Lyberg, 2009). At different points throughout the survey lifecycle, specific standards and procedures can help to ensure the quality. During the sampling phase for example, a sound and transparent sampling methodology, attention for the sampling bias and representative, etc. are topics to be addressed. Documentation on the surveys discussed here reports only in some cases about quality control procedures. However, not for all surveys, detailed information is provided.⁶ The overviews given here therefore only indicate which information is available about the used quality control procedures in the surveys, while other procedures might also be used, but not reported on. Despite this, we however also want to note that transparent and profound reporting on quality control procedures is also an important part of the quality control for a survey.

Throughout the survey life cycle, we can identify four phases in which specific attention should be devoted to quality control: during the sampling phase, the design phase, the field work phase and during the data processing phase.

Since the sampling phase is already discussed earlier, we will not go into detail on it here. For each of the surveys, it seems at the least a sound basic sampling strategy was developed. In some survey, the sampling strategy is more extensive and includes several explicit steps to enhance the survey quality and ensure representativeness of the survey.

During the design phase, activities such as pre-testing the questionnaire, or organising a meeting with experts to discuss the questionnaire design, can strengthen the survey quality. Table 3.16 gives an overview of the quality control procedures used in the surveys during the design phase. Most surveys implement one or several quality control activities during the design phase. For two surveys (LKU and ECVT) there is no information about the used quality control procedures during the design phase. Most common practices are organising a pre-test of the questionnaire and giving general attention to quality issues during the design of the questionnaire.

⁶ There is no information on the quality control procedures for the Austrian Occupational Health Monitor (AOHM). Information is also very limited for the LKU and ECVT.

Table 3.16 Quality control procedures during the design phase

Country	Survey	Test phase	Design	Control included in design	Experts involved in development	Appovement of questionnaire by experts	Translation	Review and update of questionnaire
AT	AOHM ^o							
AT	AI	*						
BG	NWCS BG	*	*	*				
DK	WEHD	*			*			
DK	WEC/DWECs	*			*			
FI	FNWHS	*	*				*	
FI	FQWLS	*	*				*	
FI	WLB				*			*
FR	SUMER					*		
FR	CT					*		
DE	BIBB-BAuA	*	*	*				
IT	ISFOL PLUS							
IT	ISFOL QWS	*						
NL	NEA		*					*
NO	LKU ^{oo}							
ES	ENCT		*					
ES	ECVT ^{oo}							
SE	SLOSH			*				
SE	SWES			*				

^o no information available

^{oo} no quality control activities during the design phase reported

Source see appendix 1

During the fieldwork phase, quality control activities are for example supervision of the interviews, follow up calls after interviews, etc. For three of the surveys, no quality control activities are reported during this phase (AI, CT and LKU). For the AOHM there is no information available. Fieldwork monitoring is a very common practice, as well as efforts to increase the response rate (f.e. reminders, telephone contact, repeated visits when person is not at home, etc.). Table 3.17 provides an overview of all the quality control procedures used during the fieldwork phase in the surveys.

Table 3.17 Quality control procedures during the fieldwork phase

Country	Survey	Training interviewers	Field work monitoring	Possibility for interviewer to launch further investigations when necessary	Follow up interviews	Check quality	Subcontracting quality control	Supervision of interviews	Subcontracting interviews	Efforts to increase response rate (reminders, several methods)	Follow up calls	Review related to methodological issues arising from interviews
AT	AOHM ^o											
AT	AI ^{oo}											
BG	NWCS BG		*			*				*		
DK	WEHD									*		
DK	WEC/DWECs									*		
FI	FNWHS		*		*							
FI	FQWLS		*		*							
FI	WLB											*
FR	SUMER			*								
FR	CT ^{oo}											
DE	BIBB-BAuA	*	*									
IT	ISFOL PLUS		*						*	*		
IT	ISFOL QWS		*			*				*		
NL	NEA		*							*		
NO	LKU ^{oo}											
ES	ENCT		*			*	*	*			*	
ES	ECVT		*									
SE	SLOSH		*									
SE	SWES		*			*						

^o no information available

^{oo} no quality control activities during the fieldwork phase reported

Source see appendix 1

Also during the last phase of data processing, attention is given to quality control procedures (Table 3.18). For most of the surveys, weights are developed and in some cases also documented. Other practices focus on the data input (monitoring, software, etc.), codification process and evaluation of the survey quality by looking at for example the validity, reliability, homogeneity of indices, etc. and non-response analysis.

Table 3.18 Quality control procedures during the data processing phase

Country	Survey	Monitoring data input	Software for digitalisation of data	Guidelines for data of incomplete questionnaires	Data processing	Supervision codification	Weighting	Non-response analysis	Survey evaluation#	Survey documentation publicly available
AT	AOHM [°]						*		*	
AT	AI						*		*	
BG	NWCS BG	*	*				*			
DK	WEHD			*			*		*	*
DK	WEC/DWECs			*			*		*	*
FI	FNWHS				*					
FI	FQWLS				*		*			*
FI	WLB				*					
FR	SUMER				*		*	*		*
FR	CT ^{°°}									
DE	BIBB-BAuA ^{°°}									
IT	ISFOL PLUS			*			*	*		
IT	ISFOL QWS						*			
NL	NEA		*			*	*	*	*	*
NO	LKU						*			*
ES	ENCT					*				
ES	ECVT				*	*			*	
SE	SLOSH									*
SE	SWES				*			*		

validity, discriminatory power, homogeneity of sub-indices, indices, item non-response, effects of data collection mode, ...

[°] no information available

^{°°} no quality control activities during the fieldwork phase reported

Source see appendix 1

4. Conclusions

This working paper is part of Work Package 21 ‘Innovative tools and protocols for working conditions and vulnerability research’ of the InGRID project. One objective of this infrastructure project is to integrate, harmonise and optimize existing tools and methods, and to create new tools to fill existing data gaps. Within the frame of the InGRID project, this working paper aimed to discuss an inventory of (national) working conditions and occupational safety and health surveys in Europe which focus on employees (individuals), looking at different aspects of the survey organisation, design, execution and quality control procedures. Together with the inventories on linked employer-employee surveys and on policy data bases on working conditions and OSH that will be made, this inventory wants to provide researchers across Europe with an overview of existing surveys, and the quality of these surveys as a starting point for further integration and optimisation of the existing tools for working conditions research.

From the discussion of the inventory, two important conclusions can be made.

The first observation is that systematic national surveys on working conditions and OSH are not omnipresent in Europe. Not even half of the EU member states have a systematic national survey running at this moment. What is more, some of these surveys have ended, without a prospect of follow-up. Thus it seems that the number of countries systematically monitoring working conditions at a national level is diminishing. This is an alarming trend, since no new national or cross-national surveys are taking their places, creating a great void of data on working conditions and OSH which needs to be addressed.

Secondly it is hard to properly assess the quality and usability of the currently existing surveys. Surveys are - logically - developed for specific purposes and with specific objectives. This will strongly influence all aspects related to the survey design, methodology, etc. Therefore it is hard to make straightforward statements on the quality of surveys, since this would be comparing apples with oranges. This report tried to give a comprehensive overview of information available on the selected surveys, to allow potential users to properly assess the usability of the surveys for his or her research objectives.

In addition we made a quick assessment of the broad usability of the selected surveys with the question in mind: which surveys are most easy to access and directly to use for a broad range of research goals (from a European, comparative perspective)? We chose for this evaluation of the surveys because we think reuse of surveys and broad use of survey data is important, since surveys and data collection is always very costly. Ensuring that a survey is used in a good way by as many researchers and for as many research questions as possible should therefore be a priority for all data collectors. In conducting this assessment we scored each of the selected surveys on six aspects which we think are important for easy access and direct and broad use of the survey (between 0 and 1) (Table 4.1):

- *continuation of the survey*: when certainty is given about the continuation of the survey, this increases to our opinion its usability for future research projects. Having access to recent data is always important and useful;
- *design (cohort or not)*: although the relevance of a cohort design depends on the research objectives, we decided to give a preference to cohort designs in our evaluation. The possibility to follow up on evolutions of among others working conditions over time is still rather scarce in Europe, despite

the fact that this will allow for more clear, causal findings on the impact of working conditions, policy changes, etc. on employees;

- *large response rate*: with a large response rate - and given a proper sampling design - both the representativity and the sample size are more likely to be good. Next to that we also think information on these elements are as important as the height of the response rate itself. Researchers using the survey need this information to properly assess the survey in terms of representativity and deal with possible limitations related to this.
- coverage of the survey:
- *available documentation*: the availability of information on the survey is to our opinion another crucial element in ensuring the usability of a survey for secondary analysis;
- *reported quality control procedures*: despite of the quality procedures which are used, reporting on them properly is to our opinion as important or even more important for future use of a survey.

Table 4.1 Evaluation of the surveys on working conditions and OSH

Country	Survey	Frequency: continued*	Design: cohort/longitudinal *	Response rate >50% *	Topics covered: working conditions & outcomes *	Documentation *	Quality control procedures *	TOTAL (0-6) *
AT	AOHM	1	0	0	0.5	0	0	1.5
AT	AI	1	0	0	1	1	0.6	3.6
BG	NWCS BG	0	0	1	0.5	0.5	1	3.0
DK	WEHD	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	5.5
DK	WEC/DWECS	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	5.5
FI	FNWHS	1	0	0.5	1	1	1	4.5
FI	FQWLS	0	0	1	1	0.5	1	3.5
FI	WLB	1	0	1	1	1	1	5.0
FR	SUMER	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	4.5
FR	CT	1	0	0	0.5	1	0.3	2.8
DE	BIBB-BAuA	1	0.5	0.5	1	1	0.6	4.6
IT	ISFOL PLUS	0	1	0	1	0.5	0.6	3.1
IT	ISFOL QWS	1	0	1	1	0	1	4.0
NL	NEA	1	0.5	0.5	1	1	1	5.0
NO	LKU	0	1	1	1	0.5	0.3	3.8
ES	ENCT	1	0	0.5	1	1	1	4.5
ES	ECVT	0	0	0	1	0.5	0.6	2.1
SE	SLOSH	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	5.5
SE	SWES	1	1	0	1	1	1	5.0

* Frequency: score 0 if survey ended or if it is unknown whether it will be continued, 1 if survey will be continued.

Design: score 0 if cross-sectional design, 1 if cohort/longitudinal design, 0.5 if a part of the survey is a cohort.

Response rate: score 0 if no response rate is reported, 0.5 if the response rate is reported but below 50%, 1 if the response rate is higher than 50%.

Topics covered: score 0 if almost no topics are covered, 0.5 if some topics related to working conditions are covered, but not all dimensions, 1 if all dimensions of working conditions, and the outcomes are covered.

Documentation: score 0 if no documentation is available (next to a website); 0.5 if some documentation is available, but not much; 1 if much documentation is available: methodological reports, questionnaire, data, etc.

Quality control procedures: 0 if no quality control procedures are reported on; 0.3 if there are only quality control procedures from 1 phase reported; 0.6 if there are only quality control procedures from 2 phases reported; 1 if quality control procedures from all phases are reported.

These scores can be summed up to a total survey score, which varies between 0 and 6. From this evaluation, four current surveys score 5/6 or more: the WEHD (and its predecessors WEC and DWECS), the WLB, the NEA and the SLOSH (and its predecessor SWES). These are not surprisingly surveys from the Scandinavian countries (Denmark, Sweden and Finland) - which are known

for their long and continuous traditions in surveying working conditions - and the Netherlands. Four other surveys scoring rather good in this evaluation are the Finnish FNWHS, the French SUMER, the German BIBB-BAuA and the Spanish ENCT.

Lower scores of the surveys are above all often related to the lack of a cohort design of the survey. This is of course not for all research questions a necessity. Hence again the fact that the quality and usability of a survey needs to be assessed from the perspective of the research objectives. Further, the response rate (or absence of information on the response rate) is also often an important problem which led to lower scores in our 'evaluation'. It is furthermore hopeful that also for the lower scoring surveys, they often are organized in a country where also a higher scoring survey exist. In other words: they are sometimes used as an additional data collection.

From this inventory it is hard to make clear conclusion about the quality of individual surveys, but we can conclude that systematic and profound surveys on working conditions and OSH in Europe are scarce, despite the importance of these topics for the European society today and in the future.

Next to the general conclusions and options for the future, this inventory of course has several limitations as well. It is not exhaustive, since only the surveys on which online information in English, German, French or Dutch could be found, are included. Therefore some working conditions surveys may be left out. The information summarized in this inventory is only based on available documentation on the surveys. The survey organisers are not contacted personally to provide additional information, check information or fill in gaps. Therefore there might be some inaccuracies and missings in the overview tables.

appendix 1 Main sources and references for the surveys

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appendix 2 Additional tables

Table a2.1 Information and topics listed in Nesstar Publisher to document data

Main menu	Submenu	Fields
Document description	Title statement	Title ID number
	Responsibility statement	Authoring entity/Primary investigator Other identifications/Acknowledgements
	Production statement	Copyright Producers
Study description	Citation	Title ID number Authoring entity/primary investigator Distributors Version
	Production statement	Producers Fundings
	Subject information	Keywords Topic classifications
	Abstract	
	Summary data description	Countries Geographic coverage Unit of analysis Universe
	Methodology – data collection	Time method Sampling procedure Mode of data collection Weighing
Other study materials		Related materials Related studies Related publications References
Datasets		
Variable groups	Description	Type Label Text Definition Universe Notes
	Variables	
Other materials		Title Location (URL) Description Notes
External resources		

Source Nesstar Publisher v4.0.9

Table a2.2 Overview all topics addressed

	AOHM	AI	NW/CS BG	WEHD	WEC/DWECS	FNWHS	FQWLS	WLB	SUMER	CT	BIBB/BAUA	ISFOL PLUS	ISFOL QWS	NEA	LKU	ENCT	ECVT	SLOSH	SWES
Background information																			
Socio demographic information		*		*	*	*			*		*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Career path		*				*	*				*	*			*	*	*	*	*
Job information	*	*		*	*	*	*	*	*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Company information	*	*		*	*	*		*	*		*			*	*	*		*	*
Working conditions																			
Work organisation																			
Contents of work							*								*			*	
Job complexity							*						*		*			*	
Working conditions							*								*			*	
Working life							*					*			*		*	*	
Work-life balance		*	*	*	*	*	*					*	*				*	*	
Nature of work			*	*	*	*	*					*	*				*	*	
Team work			*	*	*	*	*		*						*		*	*	
Contact with clients	*						*		*						*		*	*	
Mobility																	*	*	
Working time																			
<i>Working time</i>		*	*	*	*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Unusual hours</i>										*	*			*	*	*	*	*	
Work organisation												*	*		*		*		
<i>Work place</i>							*		*		*	*	*		*		*		
<i>Work organisation issues</i>				*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*		*	*	*	*	
<i>Workload</i>		*		*	*	*	*		*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	
Autonomy																			
<i>Autonomy</i>								*	*	*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	
<i>Discretion</i>	*			*	*				*			*	*	*	*	*	*	*	
<i>Decision latitude</i>				*	*						*		*	*	*			*	
Psychological work environment																			
<i>Psycho-social risk factors</i>		*		*	*					*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Emotional demands</i>		*		*	*	*	*				*			*	*	*	*	*	*
<i>Mental strain</i>	*	*		*	*	*	*				*			*	*	*	*	*	*
Physical work environment																			*

	AOHM	AI	NWCS BG	WEHD	WEC/DWECS	ENWHS	FQWLS	WLB	SUMER	CT	BIBB/BAUA	ISFOL PLUS	ISFOL QWS	NEA	LKU	ENCT	ECVT	SLOSH	SWES
<i>Safety</i>				*	*	*	*				*			*			*		
<i>Physical demands</i>	*			*	*	*	*		*	*	*		*	*	*	*	*		
<i>Prevention</i>				*	*	*	*			*	*			*	*	*	*		
<i>Accidents</i>		*		*	*	*	*			*	*			*	*	*	*		*
<i>Risks</i>	*			*	*	*	*		*	*	*		*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Employment conditions																			
Employment conditions																			
<i>Earning</i>		*	*	*		*	*	*				*	*	*	*		*	*	
<i>Conditions of employment</i>							*	*			*				*		*	*	
<i>Employment contracts</i>							*	*			*				*		*	*	
Training and development																			
<i>Training</i>		*	*					*			*	*		*	*	*	*		*
<i>Skills</i>						*	*				*	*		*	*	*	*		*
<i>Match</i>											*	*		*	*	*	*		*
Social relations																			
Participation and consultation					*	*	*			*	*						*		*
Equality		*			*	*	*			*	*						*		*
Work climate	*				*	*	*		*	*	*			*	*		*		*
Social relations	*	*		*	*	*	*		*	*	*			*	*		*		*
Violence, harassment, bullying, discrimination			*	*	*	*	*	*		*	*			*	*	*	*		*
Outcomes																			
Satisfaction																			
General life satisfaction		*															*		
Job satisfaction		*				*	*				*	*	*	*	*		*	*	
<i>Work-related attitudes</i>				*			*							*	*				
Health																			
Work related health (problems)	*	*					*		*		*								*
Health outcomes				*	*		*				*			*	*		*	*	*
Health	*			*	*	*	*	*		*	*			*	*	*	*	*	*
Absence	*			*	*	*	*		*		*			*	*	*	*	*	*
Health promotion	*			*	*	*	*		*		*			*	*	*	*	*	*
Life style and habits				*					*						*			*	

Source see appendix 1

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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Infrastructure Diffusion
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